

Representation Data without Lost Compression Properties in Time Series: A Review

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Abstract : Uncertain data is believed to be an important issue in building up a prediction model. The main objective in the time series uncertainty analysis is to formulate uncertain data in order to gain knowledge and fit low dimensional model prior to a prediction task. This paper discusses the performance of a number of techniques in dealing with uncertain data specifically those which solve uncertain data condition by minimizing the loss of compression properties.

Keywords : compression properties, uncertainty, uncertain time series, mining technique, weather prediction

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